

Splitting energy parameter ($10 D_q$), Racah parameter B and nephelauxetic ratio β of Co(II) complexes are 9830, 9408 cm^{-1} ; 1024, 980 cm^{-1} and 0.91, 0.87 respectively. Nephelauxetic ratio β happening due to the partial overlapping of 3d orbitals with orbitals of the ligand consists of both $f^2\sigma$ and $f^2\pi$, i.e. $f^2 = f^2\sigma + f^2\pi$ and are 0.91 and 0.87, showing thereby the coincidence to the values as have been observed for tetragonally distorted^{1,4} octahedral complexes of Co(II).

Infrared Spectral Studies :

I.R. spectra of the complexes as compared to that of the ligand show lowering of stretching frequencies of active carbonyl ($=C=O$) and azomethine ($-CH=N-$) groups such as 1700 cm^{-1} to 1630-1650 cm^{-1} and 1600 cm^{-1} to 1520-1560 cm^{-1} respectively, indicating the formation of complexes through these groups. Appearance of bands at 425-465 cm^{-1} and 475-550 cm^{-1} indicate the formation of metal-oxygen (M-O) and metal-nitrogen (M-N) bonds, supporting thereby chelation through oxygen and nitrogen atoms. However, peaks around 325-425 cm^{-1} are observed in the i.r. spectra of complexes of Ti(IV), Zr(IV), Hf(IV) and Th(IV), thus revealing the formation of metal-halogen (M-Cl) bonds.

The nitrate complexes of Ni(II) and Co(II) exhibit bands at 1290 cm^{-1} and 1280 cm^{-1} in their i.r. spectra, showing thereby that the complexes are nitrate-bonded^{1,5}.

The present thiocyanate complexes show i.r. bands at 2040, 2045 cm^{-1} and 800, 825 cm^{-1} indicating the coordination of thiocyanate ion with the metal ions through N-atom^{1,6}.

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Mn(II) and Cd(II) Complexes of Dicyandiamide

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As a part of our programme of investigation on amide complexes of divalent metal ions, we have reported^{1,2} complexes of lactams and nicotinamide. Dicyandiamide aroused our interest as it does not contain an oxygen donor atom even though four possible bonding sites are present. As a result, this communication reports a number of complexes of Mn(II) and Cd(II) with dicyandiamide.

Experimental

All the chemicals used are of AnalaR grade. Absolute ethanol solution of metal salts were reacted with ethanolic dicyandiamide solution in 1:2 proportion. On shaking compounds separated out in some cases, while in other cases compounds were precipitated after refluxing the solution for thirty minutes and keeping overnight.

Metal and nitrogen were estimated by standard methods. Conductance was measured in M/1000 acetone solution of the compounds. Magnetic moments of Mn(II) complexes were measured by Gouy method. I.R. spectra were recorded in nujol mulls using Unicam Sp-200 and electronic spectra by Unicam Sp-500 spectrophotometers with reflectance attachment. Relevant data are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Conductance values of the compounds in acetone solution are low indicating non-electrolytic nature, except for the perchlorate complex which has $\Delta\Lambda$ value ~ 250 mhos. cm^2 suggesting 1:2 electrolytic

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF Mn(II) AND Cd(II) COMPLEXES

Compound	Colour	M.P. (°C)	ΔM (Mhos. cm ²)	%Metal		%Nitrogen	
				Found	Calculated	Found	Calculated
1. MnCl ₂ (DCN) ₂	Light Pink	185	10.8	12.58	12.83	47.68	47.97
2. MnBr ₂ (DCN) ₂	Light Pink	206	8.4	10.45	10.78	40.02	40.30
3. Mn(NCS) ₂ (DCN) ₄	White	192	12.5	11.64	11.71	49.01	49.22
4. Mn(NO ₃) ₂ (DCN) ₄	Light Pink	178	11.8	11.38	11.53	48.22	48.46
5. [Mn(DCN) ₄](ClO ₄) ₂	Light Pink	195	205	9.86	10.07	37.31	37.64
6. CdCl ₂ (DCN) ₂	White	196	6.8	31.71	31.99	31.62	31.87
7. CdBr ₂ (DCN) ₂	White	250	6.4	25.40	25.52	25.15	25.43
8. CdI ₂ (DCN) ₂	White	250	8.7	20.91	21.03	20.78	20.95
9. Cd(NO ₃) ₂ (DCN) ₂	White	190	8.2	27.46	27.79	34.36	34.61
10. Cd(SO ₄) ₂ (DCN) ₂	White	202	11.8	28.06	28.35	35.08	35.32
11. [Cd(DCN) ₄](ClO ₄) ₂	White	205	213	23.12	23.44	46.55	46.72

nature. μ_{eff} values of Mn(II) complexes are ~5.9 B.M indicating a spin-free octahedral or tetrahedral configuration.

Dicyandiamide has the structure I

I.R. spectra of the ligand show several bands in the 3000-3350 cm⁻¹ region attributable to $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$. $\delta(\text{NH})$ appears as a weak band at 1660 cm⁻¹. $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ is observed⁹ at 1580 cm⁻¹ and $\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ appears at 2170 cm⁻¹. In the complexes there is no splitting or shifting of these characteristic bands excepting $\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ which appears around 2220-2260 cm⁻¹ region, suggesting that the ligand is bonded through the nitrile nitrogen atom. Strangely enough though there are four bonding sites, the ligand behaves as monodentate.

In the thiocyanato complexes of Mn(II) and Cd(II) a sharp band is observed at 2090 and 2130 cm⁻¹ due to $\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ mode of thiocyanate suggesting⁴ the presence of terminal N-bonded and terminal S-bonded thiocyanato group. In the nitrate complexes ν_4 and ν_1 bands occur at 1400 and 1280 cm⁻¹ region respectively and the difference ($\nabla\nu$) is 120 cm⁻¹ indicating⁵⁻⁷ the presence of monodentate nitrate group. In case of the perchlorate complexes a broad band ~1100 cm⁻¹ suggests⁸⁻¹⁰ the ionic nature of perchlorate group, confirmed by molar conductance data.

Mn(II) complexes show absorption bands ~18.4-18.6, 22.6-22.8, 24.8-25.3 and 27.8 K.K. regions assignable^{11,12} to ν_1 , ν_2 , ν_3 and ν_4 transitions respectively, presumably indicating a high spin octahedral configuration. The perchlorate complex has bands at 20.4, 22.6, 23.8 and 26.6 K.K. regions suggesting^{13,14} a possible tetrahedral geometry. On the basis of analysis, conductance and infrared spectral data cadmium complexes have a tetrahedral configuration.

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Separation and Estimation of Aluminium, Titanium and Iron in Bauxite by Paper Electrophoresis

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ELECTROPHORETIC technique has been utilised for the quantitative separation of the main constituents of bauxite, as analysis of bauxite can be